

**ARCHITECTURE OF THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE OF
SIRDARYA REGION
(as an example of 1990-2010)**

Shoisoev Izatullo Kenjayevich

*Tashkent International University
of Financial Management and Technologies*

shoisoev@bk.ru

Annotation: *The article talks about the architecture built in the Syrdarya region in 1990-2010 based on the principles of urban planning.*

Key words: *"Spirituality and Enlightenment" center, Boyovut, Gulistan, Mirzaabad, Aqoltin, "Prosperous village" and "Prosperous neighborhood" programs.*

After the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, significant changes took place in the economic and social spheres of the Syrdarya region. It is no exaggeration to say that the main factor is that the "Tashkent-Termiz" Great Uzbek Tract passes through the region. During the years of independence, important works were carried out in the field of construction, beautification of cities and villages. Reconstruction of the main square of Mustaqillik in the region, Khatira Square, buildings of Central and commercial banks, stock exchange and business centers, "Spirituality and Enlightenment" center, "Camping" type complex, modern train station, high-rise residential buildings, "Alpomish" sports palace, boxing palace, central playground, swimming pool and other sports

complexes were built. According to the national personnel training program, 303 schools, 4 academic lyceums, 45 vocational colleges and Gulistan State University are operating in the region. 173,996 pupils and students study in them. 90.8% of rural residents of the region are provided with drinking water and 84.1% with natural gas. Rural infrastructure is also changing from year to year. Due to the honor of

independence, the Syrdarya region is developing socio-economically, and the people's well-being is increasing and flourishing year by year.

The Syrdarya region of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established on February 16, 1963, and borders the Republic of Kazakhstan to the north, Tashkent region to the east, Tajikistan to the south, and Jizzakh region to the west. The topography is mainly an undulating plain, decreasing from south to north-west. A part of the Mirzachol steppe is part of the region. The height is 230 m in the north, 400-450 m in the central part, 600-650 m in the south and southwest. In the east is the wide Syrdarya valley. The area is 4.28 thousand km. According to the data of 2023, the population of the region is about 900.8 thousand people. The region includes 8 districts such as Boyovut, Gulistan, Mirzaabad, Aqoltin, Sayhunabad, Syrdarya, Khavos, Sardoba, 5 cities such as Gulistan, Bakht, Sirdarya, Shirin, Yangiyer, 6 towns such as Boyavout, Dehkanabad, Dostlik, Pakhtaabad, Sayhun, Khavos. and there are 75 village citizens' assemblies. The center of Syrdarya

region is the city of Gulistan.

Uzbekistan's bold steps towards independence and national development require that city planning, following the example of the national architectural heritage, should focus on a number of aspects such as compatibility with local conditions, beauty and comfort, and keeping up with world standards. After the independence, for the first time in history, in 1995, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on "Architecture and Urban Planning" was adopted. In the process of implementation and enforcement of this law, many sectoral opportunities appeared, and on this basis, 148 national-state "construction standards and regulations" (QMQ) were developed, taking into account the history, cultural assets, climate, earthquake and general conditions specific to our territory.

Decree of the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov dated April 26, 2000 No. 2595 "On measures to further improve architecture and urban construction of the Republic of Uzbekistan", No. 320 dated August 14, 2000 "The head of cities, district centers and urban-type settlements" related to the field of urban planning "On approval of the Regulation on the development of plans and the order of their construction" is proof of our opinion.

In addition, in 1999, the health and sports center "Alpomish" Palace, which was built at the entrance of the city of Gulistan, was built in the years of independence. The architects are R. Yakubov, G. Nefedov, R. Magay, S. Abdurahmanov. It is the most important composite object in the direction of the

entrance to the city of Gulistan. The total land area is about 2.5 hectares. Its main facade faces north, that is, Gulistan street. The main playground is located in the central part, an indoor tennis court is located in the left part, and an athletics arena and an office complex are built in the right part.

In the years of independence, in addition to public buildings such as lyceum, college, school, sports facilities, health care facilities, "supermarkets", large shopping centers, stores were established according to international standards, and the most modern construction materials were widely used in their equipment.

In 1999, "Ulgurchi Bazaar" was built in the city of Gulistan along the Tashkent-Dushanbe route, and it is serving entrepreneurs with its location on the road and its essence. Architects are A. Saakyan, S. Azizov, S. Abdurahmanov. With a total land area of 4.5 hectares, this market has a monumental appearance. In its central part is a closed sales hall, the roof of which is covered with a hemispherical dome made of lexan. Commercial premises are placed along the main facade. "Ugurchi Bazar" is entered through three entrances.

In the years of independence, under the leadership of Professor D. Latipov of the Department of "Urban Planning and Landscape Architecture" of the Tashkent Institute of Architecture and Construction, the "Development Concept of Urban Planning in the Conditions of the New Socio-Economic Development of Uzbekistan" was developed, with the participation of enterprises such as "Ozshaharzakozlit" and "Toshboshplan" enterprises. It is a gratifying fact that this important program was approved in September 2001 by the authoritative council of architecture and urban planning under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Through these concepts, the construction projects of several districts and cities in the Syrdarya region were created.

The city of Gulistan, the center of Syrdarya region, is becoming more beautiful. The central garden there was renovated and new landscape architecture works were

implemented. A statue of the famous poet Alisher Navoi was installed in front of the regional theater building, and the landscaping around it according to the latest rules made the square more beautiful. Central streets like Uzbekistan, Mustaqillik, Alisher Navoi Ahmed Yassavi were renovated and got a new modern look. In the area, both sides of the "Dostlik" canal were beautified, and the surrounding architectural composition became a symbolic gate of the Avenue of Culture and Enlightenment, and became the most beautiful park in the city center. A number of decisions and programs of state importance are being adopted in our country in order to consistently continue the creative work of the years of independence. "Prosperous village" and "Prosperous neighborhood" are such programs. During the reception of this program, it is known from the rich and ancient history of our country that the beautification and creation of neighborhoods by our ancestors is one of the most precious values and traditions.

Model residential plan consisting of 5 rooms with 1 floor in Khovos and Shirin cities, Gulistan districts

By carrying out large-scale creative works in all regions while consistently continuing these values, it is very important to create decent conditions for rural residents and improve their living culture, and most importantly, to encourage young people to do good deeds.

The head of our state expressed his opinion about the "Prosperous village" and "Prosperous neighborhood" programs, "If everyone contributes to the improvement of the house, neighborhood and village where he lives, our country will be prosperous, and the mood of people living in a prosperous country will be ensured." Despite the concentration of significant demographic, labor and economic potential in rural areas, where 49% of the population of our country is located, the "Prosperous Village" and "Prosperous Neighborhood" programs are being adopted due to the fact that the necessary conditions have not been created for them, and insufficient attention has been paid to the improvement of living standards and quality. Due to lack of radical renewal of rural settlements and lack of socio-economic development, it is an obstacle to turning our country into a modern developed country.

In recent years, a number of works on beautification and renovation of the

architectural image of central streets have been carried out in the centers of Syrdarya region and districts. These include the construction of affordable housing for rural residents based on updated model projects, in particular, the construction of comfortable houses with social and engineering infrastructure for more than a thousand families in rural areas in 2017.

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